

Aggregate modelling in the EuroMix platform

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EuroMix training material
May 2019

EuroMix methodology and tools

EuroMix handbook

- Methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment
- Examples

EuroMix toolbox

- Web based toolbox for mixture risk assessment
- Data repository

EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment

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EuroMix handbook and the EuroMix toolbox provide practical support to apply the recent OECD and EFSA guidance documents in mixture risk assessment

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

EuroMix toolbox

Web-based toolbox for mixture risk assessment

Based on previous MCRA tool

Upload toxicity and exposure data

Calculate exposure levels, relative potency factors, risk levels

A screenshot of the EuroMix toolbox web interface. At the top is a dark blue navigation bar with icons for user profile, menu, and help. Below the bar is a header image of purple grapes. The main content area has a white background with a title "Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox" and a subtitle "Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment". The text describes the daily exposure to chemical mixtures and the project's goal to develop new testing methods.

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Every day, we are exposed to a mixture of multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to health that may result from this depends on how the effects of different chemicals in the mixture combine, and whether there is any synergism or antagonism between them. The number of different combinations of chemicals in mixtures is infinite and an efficient test strategy for mixtures is lacking. Furthermore, there is a societal need to reduce animal testing, which is the current practice in safety testing of chemicals.

The EuroMix project will deliver a mixture test strategy and test instruments using novel techniques as recently proposed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. The tests will result in data needed for refining future risk assessment of mixtures relevant to national food safety authorities, public health institutes, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Chemical Agency (ECHA), industry, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders. Ultimately, this will provide information for future risk management decisions on the safety of chemicals in mixtures to be taken by the European Commission and the Codex Alimentarius.

EuroMix toolbox user manual

Web-based user manual

- Descriptions of each module
- Settings
- Data formats

A screenshot of the MCRA Documentation web page. The page has a dark blue header with "MCRA Documentation" and a search bar. A dark sidebar on the left lists the contents. The main content area shows the breadcrumb "Docs » MCRA documentation", the title "MCRA documentation", a welcome message, and a detailed "Contents:" list with sub-items.

MCRA Documentation

Search docs

CONTENTS:

- Colophon
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
- Modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix

Docs » MCRA documentation

MCRA documentation

Welcome to the MCRA 9 documentation.

Contents:

- Colophon
 - Contributors to MCRA
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
 - Modular design
 - Toolbox data repository
 - Workspaces and actions
- Modules
 - Primary entity modules
 - Consumption modules
 - Occurrence modules
 - Exposure modules
 - Hazard modules
 - In-silico modules
 - Kinetic modules
 - Risk modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix
 - Munro collection
 - Unit definitions
 - Transformations
 - Gauss-Hermite
 - Concentration models
 - Chronic exposure assessment, daily consumed foods
 - Chronic exposure assessment, episodically consumed foods
 - Unit variability
 - Screening calculation for large Cumulative Assessment Groups
 - Uncertainty analysis

EuroMix methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment

- Component-based approach
- Grouping based on toxicological considerations
- Dose addition as default model
- Relative potency factors (RPF) approach
- Probabilistic exposure assessment
- Mainly dietary exposure

Very flexible

- Also applicable for other grouping principles (structure, exposure...)
- Any type of substance
- RPFs based on ADI/TDI, NOAEL/BMD for critical or specific effect or same potency for all substances
- Methodology to handle data poor substances

Aim of the exercise

- In this exercise you will learn how to include both dietary and non-dietary exposures in a mixture assessment
- The dietary components are repeated from earlier webinar on cumulative dietary exposure
- All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

Example

- The example is based on 144 substances that have been grouped in an assessment group for liver steatosis
- Reference substance: Flusilazole
- UK Pesticide Usage Survey data were used for pesticide spray mixtures (<https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/pusstats/>)
- Simulations from the Browse model for residential exposures (<https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/browse/>)
- Limited number of simulations in the test data for demonstration

Login via MCRA 9 beta

1. [Make sure you are using Google Chrome](#)
2. [Copy https://mcra-test.rivm.nl](https://mcra-test.rivm.nl) in Google Chrome
3. Click on MCRA 9.0 beta / EuroMix toolbox to get access to the EuroMix model test toolbox

Welcome to the MCRA test environment

Please select the version of MCRA that you wish to use.

MCRA 8.3 Beta

MCRA 9.0 Beta / EuroMix Toolbox

Contact: [Prof. J.D. van Klaveren](#) National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
MCRA is developed by [Wageningen University & Research](#), [Biometris](#) for RIVM (2007 - 2019)

This project is funded by the Horizon
2020 Framework Programme of the
European Union

EuroMix toolbox registration & login

1. You first need to register as a user
2. If already registered, you can select log in now

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Every day, we are exposed to a mixture of multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to health that may result from this depends on how the effects of different chemicals in the mixture combine, and whether there is any synergism or antagonism between them. The number of different combinations of chemicals in mixtures is infinite and an efficient test strategy for mixtures is lacking. Furthermore, there is a societal need to reduce animal testing, which is the current practice in safety testing of chemicals.

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 [+ Register with your e-mail account](#)

Do you already have an account? [Log in now](#)

Insert username password

Log in

Username *
EuroMix01

Password *
.....

Login

[forgot password](#) [create an account](#)

1. Input your username and password

2. Login

Basic input for dietary exposure assessment

- Description of food, substances, recipes etc. (secondary data)
- Food consumption data
- Concentration data
- Hazard data translated to Relative Potency Factors (RPFs)

Optional

- Processing factors (e.g. peeling, cooking, juicing)
- Variability factors (correction composite samples)
- Expected or known percentage of agricultural use (occurrence patterns)

Additional input for non-dietary exposure sources

- Description of populations exposed (age, sex, etc and proportion of these subpopulations affected)
- Non-dietary exposures (dermal, oral, inhalation)
- Absorption factors or kinetic model info (e.g. PBPK parameters)

Other inputs are common to both dietary and non-dietary sources (e.g. substances, RPFs)

- Non-dietary exposures can also include multiple compounds determined from an effect-specific CAG

Non-dietary data used in the exercise

- 4 UK crops selected (wheat, sugar beet, potatoes, apples)
- Probabilistic simulations generated within the BROWSE software
 - Dermal, oral and inhaled exposure (direct from airborne spray or indirect contact with ground deposits)
 - Arable boom sprayer scenario or orchard scenario
- Combinations of pesticides sprayed extracted from Defra's UK Pesticide Usage Survey (2014)
 - All compounds in Steatosis Cumulative Assessment Group
 - Used to scale unit-dose predictions to realistic doses applied

Data formats: Dietary

Consumption data

Tables		FoodConsumption			
FoodConsumption	Individual	dayofSurvey	FoodConsumed	amountConsumed	foodsurvey
	330006559	2	A.01.04.005	25	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.02.03.006	72	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.03.01.006	26.2	VCP_kids
	330006559	2	A.05.06.015	130	VCP_kids

Concentration data

paramCode	resUnit	resLOD	resLOQ	resVal	resType	fatPerc	exprRes	progSampStr.
RF-00000128-CI	G050A	1.3	26		LOQ		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000150-CI	G050A	65.8	132		LOD		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000170-CI	G050A	10	20		LOQ		B001A	ST10A
RF-00000174-CI	G050A	64	128		LOD		B001A	ST10A

Data formats: Non-dietary

NonDietaryExposures

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	idIndividual	Dermal	Oral	Inhalation	idNonDietarySurvey	idCompound
2	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.12138307	6.97608E-05	0.001144162	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0084-001-PPP
3	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.667952515	0.000138962	0.000759811	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0203-001-PPP
4	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.075250074	0.000196423	0.001426949	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0403-001-PPP
5	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.126989226	6.86946E-05	0.000982711	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0868-001-PPP
6	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.153659534	7.65591E-05	0.000457884	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0101-001-PPP
7	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.002671139	6.13524E-06	0.000147264	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0358-001-PPP
8	ND13893_Ares_wheat	0.000483949	1.32195E-07	1.01521E-05	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0252-001-PPP
9	ND4110_Ares_wheat	0.068907975	7.58645E-05	0.002024187	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0084-001-PPP
10	ND4110_Ares_wheat	0.341684525	0.000198743	0.002649697	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	RF-0868-001-PPP

NonDietarySurveys

	A	B	C	D
1	idNonDietarySurvey	Description	NonDietaryIntakeUnit	ProportionZeros
2	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	Simulated exposures generated in Browse: BoomSprayer	mg/day	89.73185214
3	adultArableBystanderChronic_potatoes_Ares	Simulated exposures generated in Browse: BoomSprayer	mg/day	99.11999805
4	adultArableBystanderChronic_sugarBeet_Ares	Simulated exposures generated in Browse: BoomSprayer	mg/day	99.18789994
5	adultOrchardBystanderChronic_dessertApples_Ares	Simulated exposures generated in Browse: OrchardResid	mg/day	99.886122

NonDietarySurveyProperties

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Individual	idNonDietarySurvey	Individual	Individual	Property	DoubleValueMax	
2	Age	adultArableBystanderChronic_wheat_Ares	14	100			
3	Age	adultArableBystanderChronic_potatoes_Ares	14	100			
4	Age	adultArableBystanderChronic_sugarBeet_Ares	14	100			
5	Age	adultOrchardBystanderChronic_dessertApples_Ares	10	100			

unded by the Horizon
k Programme of the

Data folders

1. Click on data to view the data available for these exercises

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Typical **action types** which this system can perform are: dietary exposure assessment, hazard dose assessment and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a network of modular calculators [see Overview].

You have to organize your work in one or more **workspaces**. The work consists of specifying **tasks** of a specific action type. Tasks may need subtasks of other action types.

After running a task, **outputs** are available. Outputs are in the form of screen reports and print reports, and may also include data that may be useful as input in other tasks.

All tasks need input data, and some tasks produce output data. Data, but also saved tasks and outputs, are organised in a data repository, which includes shared items from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

WORKSPACES

DATA

Data folders

1. Click on data
2. The data folder will be unfolded (see second screenshot)
You will see EuroMix which is your own folder. You can upload your own files to this folder. For the training you click on EuroMix Training

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data / EuromixTraining01

Name	Version
(Data)	

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data

Name	Version
EuroMix01	
EuroMixTraining	

Data folders

1. The shared folder contains concentration and consumption data
2. Secondary input data needed for the exposure assessment (e.g. codes and names of foods, substances, relative potency factors or hazard doses etc.)
3. Non-dietary exposure data example + other files are for other exercises
4. When the input data is understood, go to EuroMix toolbox main page by clicking on MCRA 9 – EuroMix toolbox

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

EuroMix01

Data / EuroMixTraining

AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:42
Concentrations-fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 13:59
Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:00
HazardDose Flusilazole.xlsx	1	12-02-2019 19:47
HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx	1	27-01-2019 09:30
Imputation missing hazard dose (2).mdb	1	13-02-2019 14:43
POD-five-subst-for-training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 22:11
RPF-five-subst-for-training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:35
Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36

Go to workspace

1. Click on workspace

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

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Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

[WORKSPACES](#)

[DATA](#)

Create a new workspace

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

Workspaces

Name ▼	Tags
--------	------

Create a new workspace

1. Insert a name for the new workspace

2. Click on ok

Create new workspace

Create a new workspace, please provide a descriptive name.

workspace name *

Dietary exposure training

OK

Cancel

Create an action in the workspace (1)

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

A screenshot of the EuroMix software interface. The top bar shows "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... workspace". Below this are tabs for "Actions", "Data", "Results", and "Properties". The "Actions" tab is selected, showing a panel titled "Workspace actions" with the text "This workspace does not contain actions." The plus sign icon is highlighted with a red circle.

Create an action in the workspace (2)

1. Check to show all action types
2. Scroll down and select the action type Exposures

Create new action

Select action type

Select category

Effect representations

Effect representations are the responses which can be used to measure specified effects and the benchmark response (BMR) that defines a hazard limit for the effect.

Effects

Effects are biological or toxicological consequences for human health, that may result from chemical exposure and are the focus of hazard or risk assessment.

Exposure mixtures

Exposure mixtures are mixtures of substances that contribute relatively much to the overall cumulative exposure (potential risk drivers). The occurrence and concentrations of compounds in the same samples may be correlated, which is of importance for acute exposure assessments (Note that chronic assessments only use mean concentration values). Theoretically, this could be modelled and fitted to datasets. However, in practical applications (regarding pesticide residues) the number of positive values is commonly too low to allow such detailed modelling. Co-exposure of compounds is defined as the pattern of compounds occurring together on a single individual day. Co-exposure can enter the risk assessment through the use of mixtures of substances on a single food or by combining different food sources on a single day (through consumption).

Exposures

Exposures, possibly from both dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure, to which individuals in a population are exposed per day at a chosen target level. This target level may be external exposure (dietary exposure) or internal exposure.

Focal food concentrations

Focal food concentrations are separate concentration data for one or more focal food commodities, that will take the place of any other concentration data for the focal food in the

Show all action types

Create an action in the workspace (3)

1. Add a name, some tags and a description
2. Click Next

Create new action

Specify name/description

General

Name

Resident exposure

Tags

Spray

adult

cumulative

steatosis

Description

UK adult resident exposures from crop spray in selected crop types, with CAG for steatosis

Back

Next

Create an action in the workspace (4)

1. Select risk type chronic
2. Select Cumulative exposure
3. Include dietary and non-dietary to indicate aggregate exposure
4. Click Create

Create new action

Select tier and main settings

Exposures settings

Risk type
Chronic

Cumulative

Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure

Hazard characterisation level

Internal

Back

Create

Start aggregate exposure assessment

1. The summary window displays settings relevant for aggregate exposure
2. Go to action settings

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures / Summary

General

Name Resident exposure

Description UK adult resident exposures from crop spray in selected crop types, with CAG for steatosis

Tags steatosis cumulative adult Spray

Scope

Effects No data source selected

Foods No data source selected

Populations No data source selected

Substances No data source selected

Settings

Risk type Chronic

Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure Yes

Match to specific dietary survey individuals No

Apply correlation between identical individuals (based on id) in different No

Start aggregate exposure assessment

1. Notice that dietary and non-dietary exposures now appear as separate inputs. Their data and settings can be changed independently
2. Select Foods to start entering data (equivalent to dietary exposure example)

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures 7dc114af

Scope

- Populations (optional)
- Foods
- Substances
- Effects

Inputs

- Dietary exposures
- Non-dietary exposures
- Kinetic models (defaults)
- Relative potency factors

Target exposures settings

Risk type
Chronic

Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure

Save Changes

Specify data sources (1)

1. Click the pencil to edit data source
2. In the pop-up window, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

The screenshot shows the 'Resident exposure' interface. The top navigation bar includes a menu icon, the text 'Resident exposure' and 'Exposures action', and several utility icons. Below this is a green header bar with 'Exposures / Foods' and a unique identifier '0716d970'. The main content area is divided into two sections: 'Foods data source' and 'Foods settings'. In the 'Foods data source' section, the text 'Not specified' is displayed, and a pencil icon in the top right corner is circled in red. The 'Foods settings' section contains two checkboxes: 'Use food selection to restrict population (consumption-days or consumers only)' and 'Use food selection to restrict foods'. A pop-up window is overlaid on the 'Foods settings' section, containing a 'Browse' button with a folder icon and a 'Clear' button with an 'X' icon. The 'Browse' button is circled in blue. To the right of the pop-up window, a 'Save Changes' button and two information icons are visible.

Specify data sources (2)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open and select Secondary input data exposure.mdb

Browse datasources

☰ Data

Name	Version
📁 EuroMix01	
📁 EuroMixTraining	

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
📁 Substances		
📁 Training		
📄 Imputation missing hazard dose (2).mdb	1	13-02-2019 14:43
📄 Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36

Specify data sources (3)

1. Toggle all to select everything

2. Click Select

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

Substances

Training

Imputation missing hazard dose (2).mdb

1

13-02-2019 14:43

Secondary input data exposure.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:36

Selected: Secondary input data exposure.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single **Toggle all**

Foods

Effects

Processing factors

Unit variability factors

Substances

Points of departure

Assessment group membership models

Populations

FoodTranslations

Select

Cancel

Select an index substance (1)

1. Go to action section

2. Select Substances

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action mkennedy

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Select an index substance (2)

1. Change the index substance to Flusilazole

2. Save changes

Exposures / Substances

85ce9978

Substances data source

> Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Substances selection

Substances: 144 in scope

Substance settings

 Save Changes

Cumulative

Index substance

Flusilazole (RF-0218-001-PPP)

Select an Effect (1)

1. Go to action section

2. Select Effects

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action mkennedy

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures ada14b95

Scope	Status
(optional) Populations (15 in scope)	✓
Foods (3278 in scope) Processing types (32 in scope)	✓
Substances (144 in scope)	✓
Effects (1 in scope)	⚠

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Select an Effect (2)

1. Click on focal effect and select Steatosis-liver
2. Save changes

Exposures / Effects 87c0e689

Effects data source

> *Secondary input data exposure.mdb* v1

Effects selection

Effects: 1 in scope

Effect settings

Focal effect

Steatosis-liver (Steatosis-liver)

 Save Changes

Go back to actions

1. Go back to actions
2. Go to Dietary exposures

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

mkennedy

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Inputs

- Dietary exposures
- Non-dietary exposures
- Kinetic models (defaults)
- Relative potency factors

Select more input

1. Go to Consumptions by food as measured and click on

Exposures / Dietary exposures

8eb78c9e

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions by food as measured

Concentration models

Processing factors

Active substances (optional)

Relative potency factors

Select consumption data (1)

1. Go to Consumptions and click on check mark

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured

1b8fc060

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions

Food conversions

Select consumption data (2)

1. Select Consumption data source by clicking on pencil
2. Click on Browse to get connected to your data repository

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Consumptions

c4610dcd

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Consumptions data source

Not specified

Consumption settings

Food consumption survey

Please select a food consumption survey from the list

 Browse

 Clear

Select consumption data (3)

1. Select EuroMixTraining
2. In new pop-up window, select Consumptions data fake for training. .mdb

Browse datasources

☰ Data

Name ▾

Version

📁 EuroMix01

 📁 EuroMixTraining

↑ (Data)

📁 Substances

📁 Training

 📁 Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:00

Select consumption data (4)

1. Click on select

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

📁 Substances

📁 Training

📄 Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

1

21-01-2019 14:00

Selected: Consumptions data.fake for training.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Consumptions

Select Cancel

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Select consumption data (5)

1. Select VCP-basis as the food consumption survey

2. Save Changes

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Consumptions

3ab83c7d

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Consumptions data source

> *Consumptions data.mdb* v1

Consumption settings

Food consumption survey
VCP-basis

Use navigation panel

1. Click Dietary exposures to go back to the settings for dietary exposure

☰ Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Consumptions

Select concentration data (1)

1. Select Consumption by food as measured by clicking on check mark

Exposures / Dietary exposures

599d41e7

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions by food as measured

Concentration models

Processing factors

Select concentration data (2)

1. Click on food conversion

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured

92c4325f

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions (1 food consumption surveys selected)

Food conversions

Select concentration data (3)

1. Go to food as measured

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Food conversions

7cfe2447 ▶

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope) ✓

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Inputs

Consumptions (1 food consumption surveys selected) ✓

Foods as measured (optional)

Processing factors (optional) ✓

Food recipes ✓

Select concentration data (4)

1. Select concentrations

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured 6b41b916

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Concentrations

Foods-as-measured settings

Save Changes

Include foods with only non-detect measurements

Include substances with only non-detect measurements

Include foods with maximum residue limits

Select concentration data (5)

1. Click on pencil

2. A new window pops-up. Click on Browse

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Consumptions by food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured... fb5d7a72

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Concentrations data source

Not specified

Browse
X Clear

Select concentration data (6)

1. Select EuroMixTraining

2. A new window pop-up. Select Concentrations-fake for training.mdb

Browse datasources

≡ Data

Name ▾

📁 EuroMix01

📁 EuroMixTraining

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

↑ (Data)

📁 Substances

📁 Training

📁 Concentrations-fake for training.mdb

1

Select concentration data (7)

1. Click on select

Browse datasources ×

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining i

Name ▾	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
Concentrations-fake for training.mdb	1	21-01-2019 13:59

Selected: Concentrations-fake for training.mdb

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Concentrations Substances

Select Cancel

Go back to navigation

1. The consumption and concentration data (primary data) are selected. Go back to Dietary exposures actions settings

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures / **Dietary exposures** / Consumptions by food as measured / Food conversions / Foods as measured... fb5d7a72

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope) ✓

Substances (144 in scope) ✓

Concentrations data source

> Concentrations-klein.mdb v1 ✓

Concentration settings

Concentrations tier
Custom

 Save Changes

Select hazard data (1)

1. Click on Concentration models

Exposures / Dietary exposures

599d41e7

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Consumptions by food as measured

Concentration models

Processing factors

Select hazard data (2)

1. Get connected to a database with relative potency factors by clicking on checkmark

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Concentration models

9ad0c979

Scope

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Concentrations (14 analytical methods selected)

Foods as measured

Relative potency factors

Compute hazard data

1. Click on compute

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Concentration models / Relative potency factors

d06724b0

Scope

Substances (144 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Relative potency factors

☰ Use data

⚙️ Compute

Relative potency factors data source

Not specified

Go back to navigation

1. Go back to action settings

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures / Dietary exposures / Concentration models / Relative potency factors 1cde5695

Scope

- Substances (144 in scope) ✓
- Effects (1 in scope) ✓

Inputs

- Hazard characterisations ✓

Relative potency factors

Use data Compute

Specify non-dietary data source (1)

1. Click on Non-dietary exposures

Exposures 3fd6656c ▶

Scope

- (optional) Populations (15 in scope) ✓
- Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope) ✓
- Substances (144 in scope) ✓
- Effects (1 in scope) ✓

Inputs

- Dietary exposures ✓
- Non-dietary exposures** ⚠
- Kinetic models (defaults)
- Relative potency factors ✓

Specify non-dietary data source (2)

1. Click on pencil

2. Browse to data source

Exposures / Non-dietary exposures

87094cf1

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Substances (144 in scope)

Inputs

Active substances (optional)

Non-dietary exposures data source

Not specified

Browse

Clear

Specify non-dietary data sources (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open and select adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx data file

The screenshot shows a web interface for browsing data sources. The main window is titled "Browse datasources" and has a close button (X) in the top right corner. Below the title bar, there is a navigation menu with "Data" selected. A table with columns "Name", "Version", and "Date" is displayed. The first row, "EuroMix Training", is circled in red. Below this, there is a sub-view for "Data / EuroMixTraining" showing a directory structure with folders "Substances" and "Training", and a file "adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx" circled in blue.

Name	Version	Date
EuroMix Training		
EuromixTraining01		

Data / EuroMixTraining

- (Data)
- Substances
- Training
- adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx

Specify non-dietary data sources (4)

1. Resident data selected
2. Click Select for these Non-dietary exposures

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

- ↑ (Data)
- Substances
- Training
- adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx**

Selected: adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Non-dietary exposures Kinetic models

Select Cancel

Specify general and dietary settings

1. Four surveys are included in the non-dietary data
2. Go back to overall Exposures settings

The screenshot displays the 'Resident exposure' settings page. The top navigation bar includes a hamburger menu, the title 'Resident exposure' with the subtitle 'Exposures action', and several icons (document, gear, list, play, refresh). Below this is a green header bar with 'Exposures / Non-dietary exposures' and a red circle around the 'Exposures' part. The main content area is divided into four sections: 'Scope' (with sub-items 'Populations (15 in scope)' and 'Substances (147 in scope)'), 'Inputs' (with 'Active substances (optional)'), 'Non-dietary exposures data source' (with a file named 'adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx' and a 'v1' version tag), and 'Non-dietary exposures data selection' (with 'Non-dietary surveys: 4 selected' circled in blue). A large 'CR' watermark is visible in the background.

Adjust dietary settings (1)

1. Click on Dietary exposures

≡ Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures

Scope

(optional) Populations (15 in scope)

Foods (3278 in scope) | Processing types (32 in scope)

Substances (147 in scope)

Effects (1 in scope)

Inputs

Dietary exposures

Non-dietary exposures (4 non-dietary surveys selected)

Adjust dietary settings (2)

1. Scroll down to dietary exposure settings
2. Check Apply exposure screening
3. Click Custom and select EFSA Guidance Optimistic from the menu
4. Save changes

Dietary exposure settings

Dietary exposure calculation tier
Custom

Risk type
Chronic

Apply exposure screening

Apply processing factors

Dietary exposure calculation tier
Custom

EFSA Guidance Optimistic

EFSA Guidance Pessimistic

Test Tier 1

Test Tier 2

Save Changes

Summary overview (1)

1. Click on summary symbol to overview the data and settings before you start running the simulation
2. Check if your data selection corresponds with the information on these slides
3. Scroll down to see more (see next slide)

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Exposures / Summary

General

Name Resident exposure

Description UK adult resident exposures from crop spray in selected crop types, with CAG for steatosis

Tags steatosis cumulative adult Spray

Scope

Effects	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Foods	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Populations	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	✓
Substances	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1	⚠

Summary overview (2)

1. Check data and input settings
2. If all data and settings are ok, then go up and start running the simulation

Settings

Risk type	Chronic
Include dietary and non-dietary routes of exposure	Yes
Match to specific dietary survey individuals	No
Apply correlation between identical individuals (based on id) in different non-dietary surveys	No
Hazard characterisation level	Internal

Data

Concentrations	Concentrations-klein.mdb v1
Consumptions	Consumptions data.mdb v1
Food recipes	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Kinetic models	No data source selected
Non-dietary exposures	adultResident_NDExpCombined_small.xlsx v1
Points of departure	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1
Processing factors	Secondary input data exposure.mdb v1

Run the simulation (1)

1. After about 3 minutes you see Ran to completion

≡ Resident exposure
Exposures action

Results

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Resident exposure	Ran to completion		02-04-2019 13:16	00:02:49

Run the simulation (2)

1. Navigate to view the output results or click on Resident exposures

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Results

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Resident exposure	Ran to completion		02-04-2019 13:16	00:02:49

View the output (1)

1. Action settings shows the settings for the run.
2. Sub-action results shows intermediary results of the run.
3. Exposures shows the final result of the run.
4. Click on Exposures to view the results.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

≡ Resident exposure
Exposures action

Results / Resident exposure

Action settings Sub-action results Exposures

- ✓ Action settings
 - > Data sources
 - > Exposures
 - > Run settings
 - > Uncertainty settings
 - > Output settings

View the output (2)

1. Click on Non-dietary exposures

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox interface. The breadcrumb trail is: MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure. The main navigation menu includes: Resident exposure, Results / Resident exposure, Action settings, Sub-action results, and Exposures. The Exposures menu is expanded, showing: Exposure distribution, Exposures by route, Exposures by substance, Exposures by route and substance, and Non-dietary exposures. A red circle highlights the 'Non-dietary exposures' option.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Dietary exposure t... / Resident exposure

Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

Resident exposure
Exposures action

Results / Resident exposure

Action settings Sub-action results Exposures

- Exposures
 - Exposure distribution
 - Exposures by route
 - Exposures by substance
 - Exposures by route and substance
 - Non-dietary exposures

View the output (3)

1. Click on Exposures by route

Action settings

Sub-action results

Exposures

- ✓ Exposures
 - > Exposure distribution
 - > Exposures by route
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by route and substance
- ✓ Non-dietary exposures
 - > Non-dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by route
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by route and substance
 - > Observed individual means

View the output (4)

1. Non-dietary exposures | Exposures by route | Total distribution
2. The upper tail can also be expanded, little difference in this case

Action settings Sub-action results **Exposures**

✓ Exposures

> Exposure distribution

> Exposures by route

> Exposures by substance

> Exposures by route and substance

✓ Non-dietary exposures

> Non-dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)

✓ Exposures by route

> **Total distribution**

> Upper tail distribution

> Exposures by substance

> Exposures by route and substance

> Observed individual means

▼ Total distribution

Contribution to the total exposure distribution by route

Absorption factors are not used

View the output (5)

1. Exposures by route | Upper tail distribution

- ✓ Exposures

- Exposure distribution

- ✓ Exposures by route

- Total distribution

- Upper tail distribution

- Exposures by substance

- Exposures by route and substance

- Non-dietary exposures

Upper percentage 97,49 % (111 records), low percentile 1,452 µg/kg bw/day, high percentile 5,038 µg/kg bw/day

Contribution to upper exposure distribution by route

View the output (6)

1. Click on Exposures by route and substance
2. Select Upper tail distribution

Action settings

Sub-action results

Exposures

- ✓ Exposures
 - > Exposure distribution
 - > Exposures by route
 - > Exposures by substance
 - ✓ Exposures by route and substance
 - > Total distribution
 - ✓ Upper tail distribution
 - > Non-dietary exposures

View the output (7)

✓ Exposures by route and substance

> Total distribution

✓ Upper tail distribution

Exposure: upper percentage 97,49 % (111 records), low percentile 1,452 µg/kg bw/day, high percentile 5,038 µg/kg bw/day

Contribution to upper exposure distribution for route x substances

Non-dietary contributions are relatively small, not displayed here.

(Included in the table output)

View the output (8)

1. Non-dietary | Exposure by route and substance | Total distribution

Action settings Sub-action results **Exposures**

- ✓ Exposures
 - > Exposure distribution
 - > Exposures by route
 - > Exposures by substance
 - > Exposures by route and substance
- ✓ Non-dietary exposures
 - > Non-dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Exposures by route
 - > Exposures by substance
- ✓ Exposures by route and substance
 - > **Total distribution**
 - > Upper tail distribution
 - > Observed individual means

Exposures by route and substance

Total distribution

Contribution to the total exposure distribution by route x compound

Absorption factors are not used

View the output (9)

1. Non-dietary | Non-dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes) | Percentiles

- ✓ Non-dietary exposures
 - ✓ Non-dietary exposure distribution (daily intakes)
 - > Graph total
 - > Graph upper tail
 - ✓ Percentiles

Reference: Flusilazole, PoD = 530 µg/kg bw/day

Mean exposure: 0,0196 (µg/kg bw/day)

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage of PoD (%)	Nominal margin of exposure
50.00	0	0.00	-
90.00	0.001216	0.00	4.357E+05
95.00	0.07007	0.01	7564
99.00	0.4723	0.09	1122
99.90	1.735	0.33	305.4
99.99	3.374	0.64	157.1

EuroMix participants

22 beneficiaries from 16 countries linked to international organisations including WHO, FAO and EFSA.
EuroMix is coordinated by RIVM.

Imperial College
London

ETH zürich

